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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHIC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF PARITAPREVIR, RITONAVIR AND OMBITASVIR IN FIXED TABLET DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

Developing a single analytical method for the estimation of individual drugs is very challenging, due to the formation of drug-drug and drug-excipient interactions. The present study demonstrates the applicability of the chromatographic method to develop a new, sensitive, single HPLC method for the simultaneous quantitative determination of three antiviral agents in the fixed pharmaceutical dosage form. Chromatographic separation of the three antiviral drugs was achieved by using a gradient elution at a flow rate of 1.5 mL/min on Inertsil ODS 3V C18 column (250m×4.6mm, 5µm particle size, 100Å pore size) at ambient temperature. Mobile phase A of the gradient solvent system was KH₂PO₄ (0.03M) in 1000 ml of water and by adjusting the pH to 3.2 with dilute ortho-phosphoric acid and mobile phase B was Methanol and water in the ratio of 85:15 v/v. UV detection at 265 nm was employed to monitor the analytes. A linear response was observed for Paritaprevir over the concentration range 30–90 µg/ mL, 20-60 µg/ mL of Ritonavir and 5-15µg/ mL of Ombitasvir.

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INTRODUCTION

TECHNIVIE® is a fixed-dose combination tablet containing Paritaprevir, Ritonavir and Ombitasvir for oral administration. Paritaprevir, Ritonavir, Ombitasvir fixed dose combination tablet includes a hepatitis-C virus NS5A inhibitor (ombitasvir). The chemical name of paritaprevir is (2R, 6S, 12Z, 13aS, 14aR, 16aS) – N - (Cyclopropylsulfonyl) - 6 - {[[(5-methyl-2-pyrazinyl) carbonyl] amino} -5, 16 – dioxo – 2 - (6-phenanthridinyloxy) -1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13a, 14, 15, 16, 16a-tetradecahydrocyclopropa [e] pyrrolo [1,2-a] [1,4] diazacyclopentadecine-14a (5H)-carboxamide.

The molecular formula is C₄₀H₄₃N₇O₇S and the molecular weight is 765.886. The drug substance is white to off-white powder with very low water solubility.

The chemical name of ritonavir is 1,3-thiazol-5-ylmethyl [(1S,2S,4S)-1-benzyl-2-hydroxy-4-((2S)-3-methyl-2-[(methyl{[2-(1-methylethyl)-1,3-thiazol-4-yl]methyl} carbamoyl)amino]butanoyl)amino]-5-phenylpentyl]carbamate.

The molecular formula is C₃₇H₄₈N₆O₅S₂ and the molecular weight is 720.95. The drug substance is white to off-white to light tan powder practically insoluble in water and freely soluble in methanol and ethanol.

The chemical name of ombitasvir is Dimethyl ((2S, 5S) -1- [4-(2-methyl-2-propanyl) phenyl]-2, 5-pyrrolidinediyl) bis {4,1-phenylenecarbonyl (2S)-2, 1-pyrrolidinediyl [(2S)-3-methyl-1-oxo-1, 2-butanediyl]} biscalbamate.

The molecular formula is C₅₀H₆₇N₇O₈ and the molecular weight is 894.127.

The drug substance is white to light yellow to light pink powder, and is practically insoluble in aqueous buffers but is soluble in ethanol.

A survey of literature has revealed several analytical methods for the determination of ombitasvir and Paritaprevir in combination with Ritonavir in biological fluids and in pharmaceutical products. These include; high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). On the contrary, to the best of our knowledge, there is no method reporting the simultaneous determination of Paritaprevir, Ritonavir, Ombitasvir in the fixed pharmaceutical formulation. In this paper, we report the simple precise and accurate RP-HPLC method for the assay of Paritaprevir, Ritonavir, Ombitasvir in the fixed dosage form. The new method is capable of separating all active ingredients present in the tablet. Validation of the current method will be performed according to the requirements of USP for assay determination which include accuracy, precision, selectivity, linearity, and range.

Figure-1: Chemical structures of Paritaprevir (A) Ritonavir (B) and Ombitasvir(C).

Experimental:**Chemicals and reagents:**

Paritaprevir, Ritonavir, Ombitasvir are obtained as kind gift samples from Local laboratories Ltd, Hyderabad. Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate, methanol, acetonitrile and ortho-phosphoric acid were obtained from Merck, Mumbai, India. All the solutions were prepared in Milli Q water (Millipore, USA). Test samples composed of Technivie® film-coated fixed-dose tablet contains 75mg of Paritaprevir, 50mg of Ritonavir and 12.5mg of Ombitasvir are obtained from Gilead Sciences, Kaulalampur, Malaysia.

Equipment and Chromatographic conditions:

Waters Alliance 2695 separation module (Waters Corporation, Milford, USA) equipped with 2998 PDA detector with Empower 2 software was used for the analysis. The HPLC system was equipped with a column compartment with temperature control and an on-line degasser. Inertsil ODS 3V C18 column (250×4.6mm, 5µm, Waters Corporation, Milford, USA) and a gradient mixture of solvent A and B were used as stationary and mobile phases, respectively. The buffer contains 4.08 gms of Potassium Dihydrogen Orthophosphate (0.03M) in 1000 ml of water and by adjusting its pH was adjusted to 3.2 with ortho-phosphoric acid. The buffer was used as Mobile phase-A. Methanol and water in the ratio of 85:15 (v/v) was used as Mobile phase-B. The gradient program was given in Table-1, was adjusted at 1.5 ml/min flow rate and 10 µL injection volume were maintained. The eluted compounds were monitored at 265 nm. The column oven temperature was maintained at 25 °C. Data acquisition, analysis, and reporting were performed by Empower2 (Waters) chromatography software.

Table-1 Gradient program for the elution of Paritaprevir, Ritonavir, and Ombitasvir.

Time	Mobile phase-A	Mobile phase-B
0	90	10
3	90	10
4	30	70
6	10	90
11	10	90
13	90	10
15	90	10

Preparation of Solutions:**Standard and stock solutions:**

Standard solution of the three active ingredients of the drug was prepared in the following manner: Transfer 75mg of Paritaprevir, 50mg of Ritonavir and 12.5mg of Ombitasvir working standards into a 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolve and dilute with Acetonitrile and Buffer in the ratio of 70:30 as diluent. 5 ml of the resulting solution is further diluted up to 50 ml in a volumetric flask with diluents. The resulting solution contains 75µg/mL of Paritaprevir, 50µg/mL of Ritonavir and 12.5µg/mL of the Ombitasvir as working standard solutions. The prepared stock solutions were stored at 30°C.

Preparation of the Sample solution:

Twenty tablets were weighed and their average weight was calculated. The tablets were crushed to a homogeneous powder and a quantity equivalent to one tablet (604mg) was weighed and transferred into a 100-mL volumetric flask, extracted in diluent by sonication, and filtered through Whatman filter paper. The filtrate (5 mL) was quantitatively transferred to a 50-mL volumetric flask, and the solution was diluted to volume with the diluents.

Solutions for validation study:**Calibration and Quality control samples:**

Calibration standards (30–90 µg/ mL for Paritaprevir, 20-60 µg/ mL Ritonavir and 5-15µg/ mL of Ombitasvir were prepared from working standard solutions by appropriate dilution with Acetonitrile and Buffer in the ratio of 70:30 as diluents. Quality control (QC) samples for accuracy studies were prepared at three concentrations of the linearity range (30 µg/ mL, 45 µg/ mL and 60 µg/ mL, 75 µg/ mL and 90 µg/ mL) for Paritaprevir, (20 µg/ mL, 30 µg/ mL, 40 µg/ mL, 50 µg/ mL and 60 µg/ mL) for Ritonavir and (5 µg/ mL, 7.5 µg/ mL, 10 µg/ mL, 12.5 µg/ mL and 15 µg/ mL) for Ombitasvir were prepared from the standard solutions.

Method Validation:

The developed chromatographic method was validated for selectivity, linearity, precision, accuracy, sensitivity, robustness and system suitability.

Specificity:

The terms selectivity and specificity are often used interchangeably. The specificity of the developed LC method for quantification of all the three drugs was determined in the presence of excipients present in pharmaceutical products. In specificity study, interference between drugs and tablet excipients were evaluated from the comparison of spectral purity obtained from the analysis for the standard solutions and sample solutions.

System suitability:

The system suitability was assessed by five replicate analyses of the drugs at concentrations of 75 µg/ mL for Paritaprevir, 50 µg/ mL for Ritonavir and 12.5 µg/ mL each for Ombitasvir. The acceptance criterion was $\pm 2\%$ for the RSD for the peak area and retention times for all analytes. The system suitability parameters with respect to theoretical plates, tailing factor, repeatability and resolution between Paritaprevir peak and peaks of the other two analytes were defined.

Linearity:

Linearity of the method was evaluated at five equi-spaced concentration levels by diluting the standard solutions to give solutions over the ranges 40–120% target concentration for all three analytes respectively. The calibration curves were constructed at five concentrations of Paritaprevir (30, 45, 60, 75, 90 µg/mL), Ritonavir (20, 30, 40, 50, 60 µg/ mL) and Ombitasvir (5, 7.5, 10, 12.5, 15 µg/ mL). These were injected in triplicate and the peak areas were inputted into a Microsoft Excel® spreadsheet program to plot calibration curves. The linearity was evaluated by linear regression analysis, which was calculated by the least square regression method. The peak areas of the drugs to drug concentration were used for plotting the linearity graph. The linearity data is reported in Table-3.

Precision:

The Precision was investigated using six separate sample solutions prepared, as reported above, from the freshly reconstructed tablet formulations of the target level and the peak areas obtained were used to calculate means and RSD% values. Table-4.

Accuracy:

The accuracy of the method was determined by measuring the recovery of the drugs by the method of standard additions. Quality control (QC) samples for accuracy studies were prepared at three concentrations of the linearity range (60 µg/ mL (80% dilution), 75 µg/ mL (100% dilution) and 90 µg/ mL (120% dilution) for Paritaprevir, (40 µg/ mL (80% dilution), 50 µg/ mL (100% dilution) and 60 µg/ mL (120% dilution) for Ritonavir and (10 µg/ mL (80% dilution), 12.5 µg/ mL (100% dilution) and 15 µg/ mL (120% dilution) for Ombitasvir were prepared from the standard solutions. Known amounts of 10 % dilution of each drug corresponding to 80%, 100%, and 120% of the target test concentrations (75 µg/mL of Paritaprevir, 50 µg/mL of Ritonavir and 12.5 µg/mL of Ombitasvir) were added to a placebo mixture to determine whether the excipients present in the formulation led to positive or negative interferences. Each set of additions was repeated three times at each level. Extraction sample preparation procedure is followed and assayed against a qualified reference standard. The accuracy was expressed as the percentage of the analytes re-covered by the assay Table 5.

Sensitivity:

Limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) were estimated from the slope method

Robustness:

To determine the robustness of the developed method, experimental conditions were deliberately changed and the relative standard deviation for replicate injections of Paritaprevir, Ritonavir and Ombitasvir peaks and the USP resolution factor between Paritaprevir and the other two peaks were evaluated. The mobile phase flow rate was 1.5 mL/min. This was changed by ± 0.1 units to 1.4 and 1.6 mL/min. The effect of wavelength was studied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**HPLC method development:**

All the three-drug solutions were prepared in the diluent at a concentration of 100 µg/mL and scanned in UV-Visible spectrometer; all the drugs were having UV maxima at around 265 nm. Hence detection at 265 nm was selected for method development purpose. Some important parameters, pH of the mobile phase, concentration of the acid or buffer solution, percentage, and type of the organic modifier, etc. were tested for a good chromatographic separation. The main analytical challenge during the development of a new method was obtaining adequate retention of the polar parent compounds Paritaprevir and Ombitasvir while maintaining a reasonable elution time for the less-polar Ritonavir. Trials showed that acidic mobile phase with reverse phase column gives symmetric and sharp peaks. For this reason, potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer with pH-3.2 was adjusted with orthophosphoric acid was preferred as an acidic buffer solution. Methanol and water in the ratio of 85:15 was chosen as the organic modifier because it dissolves drugs very well. Mobile phase composition in gradient mode at a flow rate of 1.5 mL per minute was observed for a good resolution. Then a method was optimized to separate all the active ingredients by changing to Gradient mode. Several gradient conditions were tried before optimizing the final gradient program as: time (min)/% solution B: 0/10, 3/10, 4/70, 6/90, 11/90, 13/10 and 15/10. The satisfactory chromatographic separation, with good peak shapes were achieved on Inertsil ODS 3V-C18 (250 × 4.6) mm with 5 µm particles, using the column temperature as maintained at 35°C and the detection was monitored at a wavelength of 265 nm. The injection volume was 10 µL. Acetonitrile and Buffer in the ratio of 70:30 v/v) were used as diluent. In the optimized gradient conditions Paritaprevir, Ritonavir, and Ombitasvir were well separated with a resolution (R_s) of greater than 2 and the typical retention times of Paritaprevir, Ritonavir, and Ombitasvir were about 6.280, 8.432 and 10.442 respectively, the typical chromatogram of System suitability shown in Figure 2.

System suitability:

The RSD values of peak area and retention time for the analytes are within 2% indicating the suitability of the system.

Figure-2: System suitability chromatogram of combined standard solution.

Table-2: Results of System suitability study.

Parameter	Paritaprevir	Ritonavir	Ombitasvir
Retention time	6.280 (min)	8.432 (min)	10.442 (min)
Theoretical plates	60827.7	52314.9	29853.1
Tailing Factor	1.10	1.1	1.1
Resolution	---	16.6	10.2
Peak area	7795456	8210788	2349099

Selectivity:

Selectivity of the current method was demonstrated by good separation of the active ingredients. Furthermore, matrix components, e.g. excipients, do not interfere with the analytes as they have no absorbance. The representative chromatogram (Fig. 3) of the fixed dosage form solution containing excipients showed no peak interfering with analytes; moreover, the adjacent chromatographic peaks were separated with resolution factors >3 . Overall, these data demonstrated that the excipients did not interfere with the active ingredients peaks, indicating selectivity of the method.

Figure-3: Typical Chromatogram of Mixed Standard Solution.

Linearity and range:

Five concentration levels within 40–120% of the target concentration range for analytes were considered to study the linearity. The square of the correlation coefficient ($r^2 > 0.999$) demonstrated a significant correlation between the concentration of analytes and detector response.

Table-3: Linearity data for the Technivie®-fixed dosage form.

Parameter	Paritaprevir	Ritonavir	Ombitasvir
Concentration Range	29.97-89.91	19.98-59.94	4.995-14.985
Correlation Coefficient	0.999	0.999	0.999
Limit of Detection(LOD)	0.193	0.106	0.036
Limit of Quantification(LOQ)	0.586	0.322	0.109

C**Figure-4: Calibration Curves of Paritaprevir(A), Ritonavir(B) and Ombitasvir(C) standard solutions.**

Precision:

Precision of this method was determined by injecting the standard solution of the three analytes six times. The R.S.D. of the peak area of six replicates was found to be less than 2. The results obtained are shown in Table 4. In all instances, the %RSD values were less than 2%.

Table-4: precision data for Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir, and Ritonavir.

Analyte	% of the target concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	(%RSD)
Paritaprevir	100 %	0.7
Ritonavir	100 %	0.6
Ombitasvir	100 %	0.6

Accuracy:

Percentage recovery of the three active ingredients using this method was determined using the fixed-dose combination tablet dosage forms. The results of accuracy studies from standard solution and excipient matrix were shown in Table 5: recovery values demonstrated that the method was accurate within the desired range.

Table-5: Accuracy: recovery data for Paritaprevir, Ritonavir, and Ombitasvir.

Accuracy study at 80% target level	Injection Number	Paritaprevir	Ritonavir	Ombitasvir
Technivie® Film coated fixed-dose tablet was performed by preparing recovery samples in triplicate by weighing API & added to the synthetic mixture of the drug product components (Placebo) at level of 80%	1	101.3	100.5	101.2
	2	99.8	100.1	100.8
	3	101.1	99.2	99.8
	Mean	100.7	99.9	100.6
	% RSD	0.8	0.7	0.7
Accuracy study at 100% target level	Injection Number	Paritaprevir	Ritonavir	Ombitasvir
Technivie® Film coated fixed-dose tablet was performed by preparing recovery samples in triplicate by weighing API & added to the synthetic mixture of the drug product components (Placebo) at 100%	1	98.9	98.2	98.4
	2	101.8	98.4	98.6
	3	99.4	101.7	101.9
	Mean area	100.0	99.4	99.6
	% RSD	1.6	2.0	2.0
Accuracy study at 120% target level	Injection Number	Paritaprevir	Ritonavir	Ombitasvir
Technivie® Film coated fixed-dose tablet was performed by preparing recovery samples in triplicate by weighing API & added to the synthetic mixture of the drug product components (Placebo) at 120%	1	101.8	99.2	98.9
	2	98.7	101.9	101.6
	3	99.0	99.4	99.1
	Mean area	99.8	100.2	99.9
	% RSD	1.7	1.5	1.5

Robustness:

The HPLC parameters were deliberately varied from normal procedural conditions including the mobile phase flow rate was 1.5 mL/min. This was changed by ± 0.1 units to 1.4 and 1.6 mL/min. The effect of wavelength was studied. Under these variations, all analytes were adequately resolved and elution orders remained unchanged.

Table 6: Robustness Data for Paritaprevir.

Parameter	Asymmetry	Plate Count
Decreased flow rate (1.4ml/min)	1.1	60827
Increased flow rate (1.6ml/min)	1.1	63246
Wave Length	1.1	59894
263nm		
267nm	1.1	60127

Table 7: Robustness Data for Ritonavir.

Parameter	Asymmetry	Plate Count
Decreased flow rate (1.4 ml/min)	1.1	52314
Increased flow rate (1.6ml/min)	1.2	57256
Wave Length 263nm	1.1	52894
267nm	1.1	29132

Table 8: Robustness Data for Ombitasvir.

Parameter	Asymmetry	Plate Count
Decreased flow rate (1.4 ml/min)	1.1	29853
Increased flow rate (1.6ml/min)	1.1	32657
Wave Length 263nm	1.1	28946
267nm	1.1	29132

Analysis of the fixed dose combination tablet:

Twenty tablets contents were accurately weighed, their mean weight was determined, and they were then finely powdered. An amount of the homogenous powder equivalent to one tablet (604 mg) was transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask, extracted in diluent by sonication and filtered through whatman filter paper. The filtrate (5ml) was quantitatively transferred to 50 ml volumetric flask and the solutions were diluted to volume with diluent.

The amounts of Paritaprevir, Ritonavir, and Ombitasvir in ternary mixtures or dosage forms were individually calculated using the related linear regression equations.

Table-9: Assay results of Paritaprevir, Ritonavir, and Ombitasvir in tablets.

Formulation	Label Claim (mg/tablet)			Amount found in (mg)		
	Paritaprevir	Ritonavir	Ombitasvir	Paritaprevir	Ritonavir	Ombitasvir
Technivie® is a fixed-dose combination tablet	75 mg	50mg	12.5mg	74.55 mg	50.15 mg	12.5 mg

CONCLUSION

In this study, a validated simple and reliable RP-HPLC-PDA procedure was described for the assay of a complex multidrug combination consisting of Paritaprevir, Ritonavir and Ombitasvir for oral administration which is indicated as one-pill, once-a-day prescription medicine used as a complete HIV-1 treatment. To our present knowledge, no attempts have yet been made to estimate this multidrug mixture by analytical procedure. All the three active ingredients were successfully resolved and quantified using Inertsil ODS 3V C18 column (250×4.6mm, 5µm) in a relatively short run time of 18 minutes in gradient mode of the chromatographic method. The proposed method provides a good resolution between active ingredients. The developed method reported herein was validated by parameters as described in the ICH-Q2B guideline. System suitability, specificity, linearity, LOD, LOQ values, method precision and accuracy of the proposed technique were obtained during the validation studies. The proposed method has the advantages of simplicity, repeatability, sensitivity and requires less expensive reagents.

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